

PLURIDENTITIES

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Work Package 5

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Problem statement

The proliferation of technology in contemporary education has transformed language learning environments, particularly within Spanish secondary education. Technology in this context acts as an essential vehicle for enhanced pedagogical methods, enriching language acquisition through diverse tools such as mobile applications, online platforms, and audiovisual resources (Urbaite, 2024). For instance, Spanish educators are increasingly integrating technological resources (Galindo-Domínguez et al., 2023; Mena Octavio et al., 2024) in order to promote plurilingualism and facilitate the blending of linguistic practices, reflecting a move from traditional monolingual instruction towards a more holistic, multilingual framework. This paradigm shift acknowledges not only the multi-faceted nature of students' linguistic competence but also their diverse backgrounds, aligning educational systems with learners' lived experiences and enhancing their engagement. This perspective is strongly supported by the Pluridentities multidimensional framework (Pluridentities, 2025), which posits that the development of plurilingual identities is central to modern language education and is shaped by the dynamic interplay of four key components: linguistic capital, the learning environment, technology, and language policy. Furthermore, the interactions fostered by digital platforms and tools, such as artificial intelligence (AI), allow for immediate feedback and collaborative learning opportunities (Huertas-Abril & Palacios-Hidalgo, 2025).

Moreover, technology facilitates access to multilingual resources that encourage exploration and experimentation within various languages. This immersion supports the development of positive linguistic attitudes and enhances identity formation (Palacios-Hidalgo & Huertas-Abril, 2025), crucial for students navigating a multicultural society, as it is the case in Spain. However, the potential of technology in language education extends beyond mere communication tools; it cultivates a learning landscape enriched with cultural context and global perspectives, empowering students to adopt plurilingual identities and intercultural attitudes (Costa, 2024; Fountoulakis, 2024), a process that is also conceptualized in the Pluridentities framework (Pluridentities, 2025).

In considering the integral role of language learning in shaping linguistic attitudes and identities among students, it is essential to recognize the implications of social context. Language education within the Spanish context operates at the intersection of regional linguistic identities (such as Aranese, Basque, Catalan/Valencian and Galician) and the nation's overarching historical narrative, with bilingualism often symbolizing socio-political dynamics (Lasagabaster, 2017). Student perceptions of language learning are intricately tied to their socio-cultural environment,

education, and attitudes towards different languages reflect broader societal values. This interplay shapes students' linguistic identities as they navigate the complex web of language practices in their daily lives, especially when using technology (Palacios-Hidalgo & Huertas-Abril, 2025).

In line with this, it also seems essential to explore how teacher practices, particularly when mediated by technology, can influence the development of plurilingual identities and learning motivation among students. Teachers play a critical role in implementing technologically mediated pedagogies that validate and integrate students' linguistic repertoires; certainly, when using digital tools, teachers can cultivate environments that encourage the dynamic use of multiple languages in classroom discourse, leading to trans-linguistic practices that support students' language skills and reinforce their cultural identities (Ou et al., 2024). Furthermore, the strategic integration of technology, such as the use of interactive platforms and AI, can significantly reduce students' language anxiety and enhance participation (Yıldız, 2023), potentially cultivating a constructive attitude towards learning.

Ultimately, the intersection of technology, language education, and identity formation represents an evolving landscape in the Spanish educational system. With technology facilitating more adaptive, student-centred approaches, both educators and learners are positioned to engage dynamically with language learning in ways that honour their unique linguistic journeys and identities.

However, empirical research focusing specifically on adolescent students—a group at a critical juncture of linguistic and professional identity formation—remains scarce. Specifically, a descriptive baseline linking their in- and out-of-class technology use directly to their linguistic attitudes is needed to ground future theoretical work on identity within this unique cohort.

At this juncture, this working paper aims to gather profound insights into Spanish students' and teachers' attitudes and practices towards language use and language learning, and how the use of technology (both inside and outside the classroom) can be linked to attitudes and identity development. Moreover, it intends to respond to the following research questions (RQs):

- Research question 1 (RQ1). What are the attitudes and practices of Spanish students between 14 and 18 years of age regarding the use of technology (inside and outside

the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to their linguistic attitudes and identity development?

- Research question 2 (RQ2). What are the attitudes and practices of Spanish secondary-education teachers regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to students' linguistic attitudes and identity development?

Methodology

Research design

This working paper follows a quantitative research design, aiming to explore students' and teachers' attitudes and practices regarding the use of technology and its link to Spanish students' identity development. The research is guided by an exploratory cross-sectional framework (Adèr & Mellenbergh, 1999). This combined approach is employed to comprehend and clarify the viewpoints of the research participants (Schwartz-Shea & Yanow, 2012).

Participants

A non-probabilistic convenience sampling technique was employed for the selection of students. Participant eligibility was determined primarily by their proximity to the researchers (i.e., schools with which the researchers had previously made contact), a criterion that ensured operational practicality and enabled the recruitment of individuals with immediate and relevant exposure to the central research context. The main limitation of this sampling technique—its non-representativeness and the potential for selection bias—is explicitly recognised. Consequently, the findings are not intended to be statistically generalizable but are instead valued for their ability to generate preliminary insights and thick, descriptive data within the defined study parameters.

For the selection of teachers, a combination of convenience and simple random sampling was used. An initial convenience sample established a practical sampling frame of eligible teachers (i.e., teachers close to the researchers). Later, simple random sampling was applied to extend the sample size. This two-stage approach was adopted to mitigate the potential for selection bias inherent in pure convenience sampling, thereby enhancing the representativeness and internal validity of the findings within the defined participant framework.

A total of 830 students and 60 teachers took part in the study. Regarding students, 28.3% considered themselves boys ($n = 235$) and 70.8% identified as girls ($n = 588$), while 0.2% identified as 'other' ($n = 2$), and 0.6% preferred not to respond ($n = 5$). Their average age was 16.97 years ($SD = 0.740$). Moreover, 33.5% of the participating students indicated that their school was bilingual/multilingual and that they were enrolled in a bilingual/multilingual program ($n = 278$), while 35.3% pointed out that, although their school was bilingual/multilingual, they were not enrolled in a bilingual/multilingual program ($n = 293$); the remaining 30.8% of the students confessed not studying in a bilingual/multilingual school. In terms of plurilingual identity, 10.1% identified as monolingual ($n = 84$), 54% as bilingual ($n =$

448) and 35.4% as plurilingual (n = 294). Finally, 97,8% of the students revealed they were born in Spain (n = 810), whereas the remaining 2.2% indicated they were born in another country (n = 18).

Concerning teachers, 43.3% considered themselves men (n = 26), 55% identified as women (n = 33), and 1.7% preferred not to respond (n = 1). Their average teaching experience was 14.45 years (SD = 11.135). Besides, 55% indicated that their school followed a bilingual/multilingual program (n = 33), while 45% pointed out that their school was monolingual (n = 27). As for their plurilingual identity, 16.7% identified as monolingual (n = 10), 26.7% as bilingual (n = 16) and 56.7% as plurilingual (n = 34). Finally, 90% of the teachers reported they were born in Spain (n = 54), while 8.5% indicated they were born in another country (n = 5).

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Ref. No. ECHW_593-WP4-5_Phase1) and by the Ethics Committee for Research Involving Humans (Comité Ético de Investigación con Humanos – CEIH) of the University of Córdoba (Ref. No. CEIH-25-28), and all participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement.

Instrument and data collection

Two surveys, one for students and one for teachers, were constructed for the purposes of this study. Both surveys drew on items from several existing validated instruments, supplemented with additional researcher-developed questions to address study-specific aims. The selection and adaptation of items ensured both relevance to the research context and alignment with established measurement practices. Both surveys were developed by the Pluridentities consortium so as to gather information about: (1) students' background information, linguistic repertoire and language usage, sense of identification and belonging, school composition, attitudes towards multilingualism and multilingual practices at school, language learning motivation and technology for language learning; and (2) teachers' background information, linguistic repertoire, sense of identification, multilingualism and language policy at school, multilingual practices, technological skillset, and use of technology to enhance language learning among students. For this specific working paper, only the sections related to participants' background information and technology for language learning are considered.

Both surveys include different items, in some cases, expressed as multiple-choice statements or frequency selection (never–daily, also including a specific option for 'for a certain period') and, in others, using five-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree).

The student survey was distributed on paper, while the teacher survey was distributed both on paper and online, using Qualtrics XM; in both cases, it was administered in Spanish. Prior to responding, participants were informed about the objectives of the study and that their data would be used and stored exclusively for research purposes. Data were gathered between September and October 2025.

Data analysis

Once the data were gathered, they were coded and entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet to help initial data cleaning and organisation. For formal analysis, the data were then transferred to SPSS Statistics (Version 29.0 for MacOS). The analysis used simple descriptive statistics—primarily measures of frequency (counts, percentages). This initial examination served to summarise the basic features of the data and provide a foundational understanding of the participants' characteristics and key study variables before proceeding to further inferential analysis.

Results

Students' attitudes towards the use of technology for language learning

Students generally shared positive opinions about using technology to enhance their language learning. Seventy-four per cent of participating students reported that using technology, social media, or AI tools (such as ChatGPT) helped them strengthen their language skills (n = 614). Moreover, the majority of them agreed that technology could provide them with easy access to resources for learning multiple languages (92.2%, n = 765).

Regarding the use of specific technologies, around half of the participants revealed using social media in a language besides their home language (55.2%, n = 458). Although 59,3% of the students indicated they used AI tools (like ChatGPT) to practice or learn a language (n = 467), only 36.4% of them acknowledged using such tools in a language other than their home language (n = 302). In this line, 70.1% indicated they preferred using their home language to communicate when using social media (n = 582), whereas 73.3% pointed out that they watched videos or reels on social media in languages apart from their home language (n = 609). However, 21.7% of students (n = 180), showed themselves neutral about whether they used languages other than their home language when chatting or communicating with friends online.

In relation to their feelings of pride for speaking or learning multiple languages using technology, 70.5% of students were positive in this sense (n = 585), and a similar 71.1% revealed they thought plurilingualism was important when using technology, AI tools, or social media (n = 590). Likewise, 63.2% of students acknowledge that being plurilingual made them feel confident when using technology, social media, or AI tools (n = 525), 76.2% believed that using technology (like apps, games, or AI tools) made it easier to learn the languages taught at school (n = 632), and 77% (n = 639) thought that using technology made learning languages an enjoyable and fun task.

Finally, when asked about whether they enjoyed their classes more when their teacher let them use technology in the class, 68.5% of the participating students revealed they did (n = 569). Conversely, 25.4% of them showed neutral opinions in this regard (n = 211).

Teachers' attitudes towards the use of technology for language learning

In the case of teachers, they were also generally positive about the potential of technology for language learning, language use and identity development, although a considerable number of participants showed neutral opinions. For instance, although more than half of the teachers revealed they integrated technology in their classes to encourage students to connect with their

multilingual identities, such as using technology to explore not only their home language but also others (58.3%, n = 35), 31.7% of them were more impartial in this regard (n = 19). Nevertheless, 88.4% considered that technology could positively support multilingual education (n = 53), and 90% thought it could also support collaborative learning opportunities for students to practice multilingual communication (n = 54). In the same line, 73.3% viewed technology as a potential tool to reduce the challenges of teaching multiple languages in the same classroom setting (n = 44), although 20% of them were not sure about this idea (n = 12).

In relation to the integration of technology-mediated multilingual practices into (foreign) language teaching, 83.3% of the teachers believed they could improve students' motivation towards language learning (n = 50), 73.4% thought they could also raise students' intercultural awareness (n = 44), and 70% considered they could enhance learners' confidence as plurilingual individuals (n = 42). Similarly, 68.4% also felt that multilingual practices mediated by technology could improve language learning outcomes among students, although 25% were unsure about whether these could indeed impact learners' proficiency (n = 15).

A final point to consider is teachers' confidence and actual use of educational technology to support multilingualism in the classroom. In this sense, while 60% acknowledged feeling confident doing so (n = 36), only 55% confessed to actually using it for this purpose (n = 33). Nevertheless, neutral opinions were also shared in relation to real use of technology (26.7%, n = 16) and confidence to use educational technology like AI tools and apps to reinforce multilingualism (30%, n = 18).

Technology usage for language learning and teaching

Students also shared information about the specific tools they used for language learning. Figure 1 shows the main findings in this regard:

Figure 1

Students' usage of technology for language learning

Note. Own elaboration.

The most employed tools for language learning among learners were YouTube or TikTok videos, platforms such as Netflix or Spotify, and digital translation tools like Google Translate. Conversely, video games were the least used tools as indicated by learners.

Moreover, students were also asked to explain how they used AI tools when facing language learning situations. Figure 2 presents the main situations in which they used them:

Figure 2

Students' usage of IA tools for language learning

Note. Own elaboration.

As shown in Figure 2, AI was most commonly used for translation, although students also ask questions about grammar or vocabulary. On the contrary, AI-mediated tools did not seem to be frequently employed for conversation practice or writing texts.

Finally, teachers were asked to share how frequently they allowed their students to use technology in class for class-related tasks, as well as to complete assignments at home or outside of school. Results are presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3

Teacher-reported frequency of students' device use in and outside class for schoolwork

Note. Own elaboration.

In relation to the use of devices like smartphones, laptops and tablets in class, teachers indicated they generally allowed monthly, weekly and daily use among students. On the contrary, teachers revealed they generally asked students to use such devices at home or outside of school with less frequency, normally every week.

Conclusions

This working paper directly addressed its two research questions. For RQ1, findings detail students' positive attitudes towards technology for language learning, contrasting with practices favouring passive consumption over active communication. For RQ2, they reveal teachers' strong belief in technology's potential for multilingualism, alongside a confidence-practice gap. While participants perceive a link to identity development, this study provides the foundational descriptive data on attitudes and practices necessary to inform future empirical investigation into that complex relationship.

These findings offer a comprehensive view of how Spanish secondary education students and teachers perceive and engage with technology for language-related activities. In general, both groups expressed positive attitudes toward the integration of digital tools, although their practices and levels of engagement varied.

Students showed a clear appreciation for the role of technology in enhancing their language learning experiences. In this sense, they reported that tools such as social media, AI platforms, and streaming services helped them improve their skills and access multilingual resources. Their practices, however, revealed a tendency to favour passive consumption over active production in other languages, while many students watched content in languages other than their home language, fewer used those languages to communicate or interact online. This suggests that while technology facilitates exposure to linguistic diversity, it does not automatically translate into active multilingual/plurilingual engagement.

AI tools were mainly used for translation and grammar support, indicating a functional approach to language learning. Students did not frequently use these tools for more interactive tasks like conversation practice or writing, which points to an opportunity for educators and developers to promote deeper, more communicative uses of AI in language education. Despite this, learners expressed strong emotional connections to their multilingualism, associating technology use with pride, confidence, and enjoyment when learning languages. Their responses also highlighted the motivational impact of technology in the classroom, with many indicating that technology-mediated lessons were more enjoyable than more traditional ones.

As for teachers, they also recognized the potential of technology to support multilingual education. They believed that digital tools could foster collaborative learning, reduce challenges in multilingual classrooms, and enhance learners' motivation, intercultural awareness, and

confidence. However, their actual practices did not always align with these beliefs because many felt confident using technology to promote multilingualism, and fewer reported doing so regularly. Neutral attitudes towards implementation and confidence suggest that more support and training may be needed to bridge the gap between intention and practice.

Moreover, teachers revealed allowing students to use devices like smartphones and tablets in class with some regularity, but were more conservative about assigning technology-based tasks outside of school. This may reflect concerns about access, distractions, or pedagogical control. Nonetheless, their openness to integrating technology in the classroom indicates a willingness to develop teaching practices in line with students' digital preferences.

Taken together, these findings reveal a shared belief in the value of technology for language learning and identity development, and in turn highlight areas for growth. The interplay between student practices, teacher beliefs, and institutional support mirrors the dynamic connections within the Pluridentities framework (Pluridentities, 2025), particularly the need for better alignment between technology, language policy, and the learning environment to fully leverage students' linguistic capital. On their part, teachers are optimistic about the benefits of digital tools, but may require more resources and training to fully realize their potential in fostering plurilingualism.

The implications of this research point to several key steps. Firstly, educational policies should encourage the active use of multiple languages in digital contexts, moving beyond passive exposure to promote meaningful communication and creative expression. Secondly, teacher training programs should focus on building confidence and competence in using technology to support multilingual practices and plurilingual students. Thirdly, curriculum designers should integrate digital tools in ways that reflect students' preferences and habits, making language learning more engaging and relevant. Finally, schools must address issues of equity and access to ensure that all students can benefit from technology-enhanced language education, both inside and outside the classroom. By embracing these directions, Spanish secondary education can benefit more from the power of technology to cultivate confident, motivated, and plurilingual learners prepared for a digitally connected world.

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